

EXPERIMENTER EFFECT IN A GUIDED BREATHING EXPERIMENT

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ABSTRACT

Guided breathing is a widely used technique for relaxation and stress recovery and a core feature of many biofeedback applications. The design of feedback cues to support guided breathing has received significant attention and there are several proposals using different feedback modalities and their combinations. Studies that investigate the effectiveness of such designs are often done in the laboratory under supervision by the experimenter. Even though it is known that the presence of the experimenter is a factor that may influence participant performance, the extent to which such an effect appears in guided breathing experiments is unknown. To examine this possibility, we designed an experiment in which participants performed guided breathing in the laboratory with and without supervision by the experimenter. The results indicate that the presence of the experimenter affected the stress levels reported by participants and the efficacy of guided breathing which increased when participants performed the experiment unsupervised.

1. INTRODUCTION

Guided breathing is an increasingly focal factor in e-health and is often found in biofeedback applications [1]. Slow breathing helps regulate stress levels [2] and can lead to improved physical and mental health [3]. Numerous commercial applications (e.g., Inner Balance, emWave2, my-Breath, Pranayama), games e.g., [4], tangible interfaces e.g., [5], or virtual reality and artistic interventions [1] use breathing biofeedback. Convenience users, veterans [6], drivers [7], children [8], students [9], athletes [10], and other user groups [2] have benefited.

Breathing biofeedback may be delivered in an open and/or a closed loop. In closed loop applications, users typically adjust their breathing while monitoring relevant psychophysiological parameters. These are often related to stress and include respiration rate, electrodermal activity, heart beat, heart rate variability (HRV), or their derivatives. In open loop applications, users adjust their breathing based on visual, auditory, tactile, or multimodal guided breathing cues.

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Several feedback designs have been proposed in the literature but not all studies evaluate the efficacy of the feedback cues in guiding breathing. It appears though that auditory, visual, and haptic modalities can be used to deliver guided breathing cues equally well [11]. The efficacy of guided breathing cues is typically evaluated in controlled experiments conducted by an experimenter in the laboratory, a common practice in behavioral research. However, existing studies suggest that the presence of an experimenter may influence participants' behavior and the outcome of the experiment [12]. This may be especially important in experiments that evaluate technology that aims to modulate private, covert, and potentially sensitive aspects of behaviour such as stress but also the emotions or well-being of participants.

Given this motivation, our research question investigates the extent to which the presence of experimenter may affect the stress levels reported by participants and the resulting efficacy of guided breathing cues in a controlled experiment. The article is organized as follows. First, we provide background on both breathing biofeedback and on the experimenter presence effect on which we ground our research question. Subsequently, we present a quantitative evaluation study, the results, and a discussion of the findings.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Designing Guided Breathing Cues

Guided breathing is a very old technique for effecting our psychophysical state used to both relax but also agitate people. Slow or deep breathing, in particular, is often used for calming down people, commonly in situations that may lead to increased stress. The design of guided breathing techniques has been receiving increased interest during the design of biofeedback applications providing feedback cues for guided breathing.

Feedback for performing guided breathing can be provided visually using simple geometric shapes [2], written instructions or an animation indicating breathing phases, for example, an opening and closing circle as a cue for inhaling or exhaling e.g., [6]. Other researchers propose using peripheral visual cues such as modifications in background screen lighting or brightness [13]. Visual feedback for guided breathing may also involve more complex animations as done when creating biofeedback games e.g., [8] or virtual reality scenes and installations [1]. Auditory

feedback providing guided breathing cues can be speech instructions that cue to breathing phases, non-speech sound such as metronome or simple tones [14], musical sound e.g., [15], but also modulated pink or white noise [16]. Breath-like cues have also been used to guide breathing [17]. The use of music is also common in which case musical parameters are modulated to provide subliminal cues to a desired breathing rate. Multimodal cues may appear in commercial applications (e.g., Breathing Zone, Breathe+), but also in guided breathing videos found on online platforms, but also researcher papers e.g., [16]. Audiovisual cues are very common as they are easy to provide in contemporary devices [18]. Audio, visual, and audio visual cues can work equally well in guiding slow breathing [11]. Tactile, force-feedback, and pneumatic cues have also been used with success [16,19,20].

2.2 The Experimenter Presence Effect

The experimenter, or experimenter presence, effect relates to possible interference in the performance of a test subject during an experiment due to the presence of the experimenter. In their review, Guerin [12] discuss the 'mere presence' effect as one of several cases of social facilitation in performance. They report that the majority of the studies in which the experimenter watched the subject found effects of the experimenter presence. These are likely due to evaluation apprehension, self-presentation, or self-attention effects [12]. They note that it is common that experimenters are viewed as experts, even if they are not, and suggest that the 'presence of a conspecific can increase the drive or arousal of a person because of the uncertainty in the conspecific's behaviour' [12]. Task-specific mediating factors, such as ceiling effects or predictable observer behavior, can potentially limit the size of the experimenter presence effects [12]. For example, a lack of evaluative perception by participants may reduce the influence of experimenter presence. Klein et al. in their review [21] et al also suggest that the experimenter presence influences participant performance. Participants may be influenced to behave in accordance with what they believe experimenters want and try to be "good" subjects [22]. Slight changes in overt behavior of the experimenter between conditions can also influence outcomes.

The experimenter presence may be facilitating to task performance but not necessarily so, especially for more complex tasks [12]. More recently, Belletier et al [23] look into resource limitations due to the presence of others while performing complex tasks focusing on potential impact on the working memory. They used a memorization task and also introduced a secondary task to reduce availability of attention. Concurrent articulation was introduced in some conditions to prevent the use of verbal rehearsal. An effect of the experimenter presence appeared only when verbal rehearsal was prevented indicating that social presence hinders attentional but not non-attentional maintenance in working memory. Garcia-Marques et al [24] in their meta-analysis also find that social presence modulates Stroop interference. Stroop interference is observed in the context of the Stroop task which involves the presentation of a list

of words used as color names (e.g., red, green, etc) that are printed in ink colors that may or may not match the color associated with the presented word. Participants exhibit lower Stroop interference when performing the task in the presence of others than in isolation. The effect was stronger with an attentive audience compared to an inattentive one and null for an evaluative audience. The latter finding may, however, be task-specific as performance in a Stroop task is less sensitive to motivational factors. Interestingly, even if there is evidence that the experimenter presence may modulate results, in their review, Palmer et al [25] find that the majority of articles in behavioural studies do not specify the exact conditions related to experimenter presence. Research shows that experimenter presence influences behavior and stress responses in both humans and animals, highlighting the universal nature of this effect [12,26]. Further evidence from digital health studies emphasizes that human interaction, even when minimal, can enhance engagement and outcomes, particularly in therapeutic settings where participant motivation is critical [27]. These findings underscore the importance of investigating how experimenter presence impacts outcomes in stress-modulating interventions, such as guided breathing. Our study uniquely examines these effects on self-reported stress relief and biofeedback outcomes.

2.3 Summary and Research Question

The literature indicates that visual, auditory, tactile but also multimodal cues have often been used in guided breathing applications and can successfully guide users to perform slow breathing. Slow breathing is known to have the ability to help users calm down, reduce stress, and thus improve their health and well-being. Starting from initially simple cues and instructions, researchers are designing increasingly complex cues using different modalities in different settings. The effectiveness of guided breathing cues needs often to be validated and this process takes place in the laboratory most often in the presence of an experimenter who oversees the experiment.

However, research indicates that the performance of participants may be modulated by the very presence of the experimenter [12,21,26]. It also shows that the experimenter presence effect is task dependent and can be facilitating but also detrimental to task performance while it depends on several parameters related to how the subject perceived the experimenter as well as the specific design of the experiments. The extent to which such an effect will appear in a novel experimental context is very hard to predict without collecting empirical data. As a first step in investigating the impact of the presence of the experimenter on guided breathing, we seek here to identify whether the presence of the experimenter may modulate self-reported stress level and the reported efficacy of the feedback cues during the performance of a guided breathing task.

3. METHOD

As mentioned above, the research question we want to answer is how the presence of an experimenter influences

Figure 1: An illustration of the stimuli used in the experiment. The top panel shows instances of the visual stimulus which consisted of oscillating concentric circles of variable radius. The middle panel shows the auditory waveform and the diminishing loudness cues. The lower panel is the spectrogram showing the bell sound and its harmonics and the drone of rising and falling pitch contour.

Figure 2: Setup of test sessions. I is introduction, S1-S2 are stressor trials (1min 15 sec) and T1-T2 are test guided breathing trials (2 min).

stress modulation during guided breathing tasks. Unlike previous studies, which examined experimenter presence broadly in behavioral contexts [12], this research applies the concept to guided breathing. The research question was evaluated in a controlled experiment. By systematically varying experimenter presence, we aim to understand its impact on stress relief outcomes, providing critical insights for both supervised and self-guided interventions.

The experiment contained both stressor and guided breathing (test) trials. This is not uncommon in the design of experiments that evaluate the efficacy of interventions aiming to reduce stress. The goal is to increase the participants' stress level in the stressor trials so that the efficacy of the intervention can be assessed right after by exposing participants to the treatment (in our case the guided breathing stimulus) in the test trials.

The experiment followed a mixed design with two independent variables. The first was feedback *modality* which was within-subjects and had two levels: visual and auditory. The second was *experimenter presence* and was between-subjects. It had two levels (supervised and unsupervised). There were two dependent variables. The first was the reported stress level of users measured using a Visual Analog Scale (VAS), a common and reliable way to assess stress [28]. The second was stress load and stress relief, calculated as the difference in reported stress levels after exposure to the stressor and the guided breathing stimulus, respectively. By comparing the values of both dependent variables in the supervised and unsupervised conditions, we attempted to establish whether the presence of the experimenter had a significant effect and exactly how it affected the reported levels in the experimental trials.

3.1 Stimuli

Figure 1 shows the visual and auditory stimuli used in the test trials. The visual stimulus consisted of concentric circles whose radius increased throughout the inhale phase and decreased throughout the exhale phase. When stimulus modality was visual, a static drone sound without any cues to the breathing cycle was played in the background to provide a similar context as in the auditory conditions. The auditory stimulus consisted of a bell sound which signaled the beginning of the inhale and of the exhale breathing cycles. The bell's pitch was higher in the inhale compared to the exhale phase. An additional cue was given by a white-noise based drone signal whose pitch swept upwards during the inhaling phase and downwards during the exhale phase. The drone signal was heard over an ambience of stacked notes whose amplitude was modulated by slow moving LFOs. These notes were in harmony with the alternating entrainment sounds. The circle used in the visual condition was also shown in the auditory condition. However, it remained static and provided no cues to the guided breathing.

In the stressor trials, participants watched a video which instructed them to perform a number of mental arithmetic operations under time pressure while listening to a distressing sound stimulus (a sawtooth wave with a fundamental that swept upwards increasing to uncomfortable levels to accentuate the effect and the time pressure) and report the result. Mental arithmetic under time pressure is often used to induce stress e.g., [29]. Test trial duration was 2 minutes and stressor trial duration 1 minute and 15 seconds. The stimulus was prepared for a slow (5 breaths per minute) respiration pace.

3.2 Participants

Two groups of 16 healthy adults ($\mu = 26.4$ years, $\sigma = 7.47$ years, 20 male, 12 female) participated in the study. Subjects did not report any respiration problems. They provided informed consent before the experiment. Participation was voluntary and could be terminated at any time.

Figure 3: a. Absolute VAS stress level on test (guided breathing) trials. b. Difference in VAS stress level after test (guided breathing) trials. c. Absolute VAS stress level on the stressor trials. d. Difference in VAS stress level after stressor trials. Brackets indicate standard error.

3.3 Procedure

Each experiment session started with explaining what will happen in the experiment followed by a demonstration of breathing along the stimuli from the experimenter. Subsequently, the interleaved test and stressor trials were presented as illustrated in Figure 2. The order of presentation of the feedback modalities was counterbalanced across participants. When participants were supervised the experimenter remained in the room, otherwise the experimenter left the room as soon as instructions were given and the demonstration was finished. The subjects could call the experimenter as soon as the test was finished. After completing a test or stressor trial participants provided a stress rating on a VAS scale between 0 and 100. Each session lasted about 1 hour. Participants entered stress levels using the VAS also before engaging in the first trial.

3.4 Instructions

At test trials, participants were instructed to 'Try to relax and sync your breath to the stimuli in the video'. After exposure to each video participants were instructed to 'Enter how stressed you feel using the slider below'. In the stressor trials, participants were instructed to perform the mental arithmetic task while listening to the sound played.

3.5 Setup

The stimuli for the test and stressor trials were prepared and stored in video files. The order of presentation was controlled by a MAX/MSP patch running on a PC. The patch guided participants through the trials. In each trial, participants pressed a button when ready to start. This triggered the display of the relevant video which was either a stressor or a test video containing auditory or visual cues as appropriate. After exposure, participants indicated their perceived stress level using the VAS which was displayed as a slider on the screen. The experiment was performed in a quiet laboratory environment. Sound was played by a Steel Series headset.

3.6 Hypotheses

We hypothesize that (H1) reported stress levels will be reduced after exposure to the guided breathing stimuli in the test trials and (H2) increased due to exposure to the stressor stimuli in the stressor trials. Furthermore, we hypothesized (H3) that an effect of experimenter will be observed, as this is the most common finding in the literature. Given that we were not able to find a similar experiment in the literature, we did not form a hypothesis with respect to the direction of the effect.

4. RESULTS

The dataset we analyzed consisted of the participant stress levels reported using the VAS after each stressor or test trial as well as the stress relief or load data, estimated as the difference in the reported stress levels (VAS) after and before being exposed to the stimulus presented in each test and stressor trial, respectively. Data can be seen in Figure 3. The presentation of the results and the statistical analysis is centered on examining the effect of the experimenter presence.

A check for outliers was performed using the `boxplot.stats` function of R. This removed 2 out of the 128 reported stress level data points (VAS scale) and 12 out of the 128 stress load and stress relief data points. The underlying distribution of the data sets in each condition was examined visually and using a Shapiro-Wilk test. When analyzing the VAS scale data, in 6 out of the 8 conditions the hypothesis that data come from a normal distribution was rejected and non-parametric tests were used. When analyzing the stress relief and load data, this happened in only 2 out of the 8 conditions, and given the robustness of ANOVA to small violations in the assumptions, we performed a parametric test.

Figure 3a illustrates reported stress levels in the guided breathing trials. On average, reported stress levels were lower in the unsupervised condition. The effect of experimenter presence was examined using a Kruskal-Wallis test and turned out to be significant, $\chi^2(1) = 3.8911$, $p = 0.048$ thus reported stress levels after exposure to the guided breathing stimulus were significantly lower when unsupervised. In Figure 3b, the stress relief due to exposure to the guided breathing stimulus is shown. We see that exposure to the guided breathing stimulus reduced stress levels. The extent to which the reduction was significantly different than 0 was examined using a t-test. The outcome was significant ($p < 0.01$) for all conditions in the experiment. Again, stress relief appears to increase in the unsupervised conditions. A 2-way mixed ANOVA with *modality* as within-subjects factor and *presence* as a between-subjects factor was performed showing that the effect of *experimenter presence* was significant, $F(1,30) = 5.27$, $p = 0.028$, $\eta^2 = 0.12$. Stress relief was significantly higher when unsupervised.

In Figure 3c, we see the reported stress level after exposure to the stressor stimulus. On average, a higher stress level after exposure is reported when unsupervised. The effect of experimenter presence was examined using a Kruskal-Wallis test but turned out not to be significant ($p = 0.23$). In Figure 3d, stress load is reported. On average, exposure to stressor trials increased stress load. The extent to which the increase was significantly higher than 0 was examined using a t-test. The outcome was significant ($p < 0.01$) for all conditions in the experiment. Again, a 2-way mixed ANOVA with *modality* as within-subjects factor and *experimenter presence* as a between-subjects factor was performed on the stress load. The effect of *experimenter presence* was significant, $F(1,30) = 10.45$, $p = 0.002$, $\eta^2 = 0.20$. Reported stress load was significantly higher when participants were unsupervised.

5. DISCUSSION

This study was a first step in examining whether the presence of the experimenter may have an effect on reported stress levels during a guided deep breathing experiment. In a controlled experiment, participants took part in interleaved stressor and guided breathing trials which were either supervised or unsupervised by the experimenter. Participants reported their perceived stress level using a visual analogue scale after each trial was completed. Stress load and relief were calculated as the difference in reported stress levels before and after exposure to a guided breathing test or stressor stimulus. We examined the effect of experimenter presence for both the absolute reported stress level (VAS scale data) as well as for stress load and relief.

Reported stress level increased significantly after exposure to the stressor trials and decreased significantly after exposure to test trials. This is in accordance with hypothesis H1 and H2.

Focusing on the guided breathing trials, we did find a significant effect due to the presence of the experimenter both when examining reported stress levels (VAS data) and when examining stress relief data. When unsupervised, participants reported significantly lower stress after exposure to the guided breathing stimulus compared to when supervised. Stress relief was also significantly higher when unsupervised compared to when supervised. Focusing on the stressor trials, the effect of the experimenter presence was significant when analyzing stress load. Furthermore, participants also reported higher stress levels after exposure to the stressor when unsupervised compared to when supervised, however, the effect was not significant.

Taken together, these results provide evidence for the existence of an experimenter presence effect in guided breathing experiments. The effect was most evident in conditions in which participants were exposed to the guided breathing stimulus in which case it was significant for reported stress level (VAS) and stress relief. In the stressor trials, even if a similar tendency appears in the reported stress level (VAS), the effect was only significant when analyzing stress load. Concluding, it can be argued that the reported findings are in agreement with the trend for observing a significant effect due to the presence of the experimenter in the behavioural studies in the literature [12] and partially confirm H3.

Some interesting observations can also be made concerning the direction of the effect. The tendency is to report significantly lower absolute stress levels after exposure to the guided breathing stimulus when unsupervised compared to when supervised. Reported stress relief is also significantly higher when unsupervised compared to when supervised. A similar tendency appears for the stress load data, which is also significantly higher when unsupervised compared to when supervised. Taken together, these results imply that the presence of the experimenter may reduce the reported efficacy of the intervention. A similar, even if not significant, tendency is similar for the reported stress levels, as these are higher when unsupervised compared to when supervised.

Concluding, the findings of this study highlight the nu-

anced role of the experimenter presence in guided breathing interventions and raise broader questions about how the delivery of auditory design strategies and facilitation methods impact user engagement and intervention efficacy. In practical applications, the way interventions are delivered, whether through a personalized session curated by a facilitator, AI-driven customization, or generic pre-recorded content, could profoundly influence the perceived relevance and efficacy of the experience. These aspects will be the objective of future investigations in this topic.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Motivated by the different findings in the literature pertaining to the effect of the experimenter presence, we performed a controlled evaluation study in which participants performed guided breathing with and without an experimenter being present. We measured reported stress level after exposure to the test stimuli or stressor trails. Exposure to the test stimuli and stressor trials worked as expected and stress levels respectively decreased and increased. The results provide supportive evidence with respect to a significant effect due to the presence of the experimenter. Specifically, the presence of the experimenter affected significantly reported stress levels in the guided breathing trials as well as stress relief and stress load in both guided breathing and stressor trials. Participants tended to report a lower efficacy of the test and stressor stimuli when the experimenter was present. Future research will look into verifying this result in the light of evidence from physiological data.

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